

Time and Particle Force in Quantum and Classical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 11, 2021

Classical mechanics describes a particle's reaction to a force at each $x(t)$. One knows position, velocity, acceleration etc at each point in time with an external force governing this motion. In a previous note (1) we argued that in quantum mechanics time and space are decoupled and secondly that one should consider a quantum particle as trying to create its own "potential" within a region of its wavelength (which we argued was based on a physical sensing of two dimensions - from $\exp(ipx)$ - with one along p (momentum) and the other in a plane perpendicular to p . In this note we also argue that a similar phenomenon appears in classical physics, namely in the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in a spinning cylindrical container.

At first these two viewpoints seem to be completely different. In this note we argue that classical physics may also be thought of in terms of a particle establishing its own "potential" or force based on its momentum at each $x(t)$. In other words, the wavelength does not come into play creating crests and troughs as it does in the quantum scenario (or it cannot be resolved), but a "force" or potential based on p which is linked to impulse does exist. We further argue that the decoupling of time in quantum mechanics is linked to the wavelength which is large with respect to dx in quantum mechanics. In classical mechanics, the wavelength, which still exists, is tiny compared with dx and so time is linked to average position (velocity) values and time and space are not decoupled. (Technically they are not decoupled in quantum mechanics if one uses the rms velocity instead of instantaneous velocities associated with $\exp(ipx)$.)

Decoupling of Space and Time in Quantum Mechanics and the Link to Wavelength

A quantum particle differs from a classical one in a number of respects, one of them being wavelength. In (1) we argued, that similar to spin which senses three spatial directions, the wavefunction for a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ senses two dimensions (associated with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$). One is in the direction of motion p and the other in a plane perpendicular like the electric field of a photon. The wavelength is proportional to $1/p$ and so we argue there is some physical mechanism of a quantum particle which allows it to detect distances within the range of a wavelength. This means that there is a certain nonlocality associated with a quantum particle which does not appear for a classical particle and so the quantum particle creates a spatial profile based on $\exp(ipx)$. This becomes strong measurable if interference occurs. One may note that if momentum is high, the wavelength is small and this may essentially remove the idea of nonlocality if dx is much larger than the wavelength. Thus quantum features may disappear (become unresolvable) in a classical limit.

A wavelength appreciable to quantum length scales (10 power -10 m or 10 power -15 m etc) suggests a quantum particle has a probability to be within a certain wavelength length region even though it is moving with a constant p . This is a very different idea from those of classical physics. If one considers $v=x/t=\text{constant}$, then different x values within this wavelength range correspond to different times. Thus one does not really have a fixed time. As result of this ambiguity, $\exp(ipx)$ probability values interfere or superpose and one may even have $\exp(ipx)$ interfere with $\exp(-ipx)$ even though classically these are clearly separated in time.

If one considers the classical Action for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic) i.e.

$$\text{Action} = -Tm_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \text{ with } c=1 \text{ or } \text{Action} = T \cdot 5mvv$$

and uses $v=x/t$ with x and t being independent, then $d\text{Action}/dt=-E$ ((0a)) and $d\text{Action}/dx = p$ ((0b)). While taking derivatives d/dx and d/dt , x and t are independent, but after, x/t is set equal to v . Technically x and t should not be independent, but making them independent leads to the interesting results ((0a)) and ((0b)) which in turn allow for the creation of linear differential equations for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases namely the Klein-Gordon and free particle Schrodinger equation. These in turn incorporate the idea of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ so the decoupling of x and t seems to be linked to the nonlocality in space i.e. the wavelength.

Idea of Particle Force

In (1) we argued that a central idea of quantum mechanics seems to be the scenario of a particle establishing a “kind of potential” based on impulse and $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a “kind of spatial probability”. We noted that a potential $V(x)$ may be decomposed into $\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. The wavefunction of the free particle $\exp(ipx)$ is of the same form and is linked to an impulse hit of p just as $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x)$ is linked to an impulse hit of k . Both $V(x)$ and the particle must have an intrinsic force e.g. the electrostatic or nuclear strong force, but the impulse (i.e. momentum) is also critical to the overall impact. We argue that quantum mechanics is based on the momentum impulse linked with the nonlocality contained in $\exp(ipx)$. Thus a physical density is created if there is interference. For $V(x)$, one has a particle momentum distribution $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $W^*(x)W(x)$ or $W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state yields a density pattern which may have peaks and troughs as in the oscillator case. Given that the particle has momentum, this density pattern leads to regions with high density multiplied by the average momentum squared (to create pressure) in this region. Thus quantum mechanics leads to a somewhat complicated “particle potential” scenario.

For example, one way to create an average in quantum mechanics is:

$$\langle W(x) \text{ Operator } W(x) \rangle \text{ or for Kinetic energy} = \langle W(x) -1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x) \rangle \quad ((1))$$

((1)), however, is equivalent to: $\text{density} * KE(x)$ ((2)) where $\text{density} = W^*(x)W(x)$ and

$$KE(x) = [\text{Sum over } p a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)] \quad ((3))$$

$KE(x)$ is equivalent to the classical kinetic energy (at x) value. In the case of a two slit system, the quantum particle senses distances within a wavelength and tries to establish a “kind of potential” within the geometry of the two slits which leads to an interference pattern which carries through space. As a result, at a screen far away there are crests and troughs. The crests

represent high probability of particle presence which is multiplied by the momentum squared at such a point to calculate the pressure (2).

We argue that classical mechanics is also based on a particle “force or potential”. The difference (from quantum mechanics) is that the wavelength is so tiny with respect to dx , that one does not deal with high and low density regions. They are unresolvable. At dx , one imagines one particle which carries a momentum which represents part of an impulse force if the particle hits a wall for example. Momentum differs at each x due to the external force so one really has a “particle force” profile through x similar to the quantum scenario, but missing the humps and troughs which cannot be seen due to low resolution in the classical scenario.

Classical Analogy

The idea of a quantum particle creating a “kind of potential” due to the superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ probability waves seems to have an analogue in classical physics. Consider a cylinder containing a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and let it rotate about its axis. From classical statistical mechanics:

Spatial density = $\exp(-V(r)/T)$ where T is temperature ((4))

The potential is equivalent to $.5m\omega^2 r^2$ where r is measured perpendicular to the axis of rotation. Then Force = $-d/dr .5m\omega^2 r^2 = -m\omega^2 r = -mv^2/r$. The density profile creates the centripetal force needed to hold the particles in circular motion. At first glance ((4)) has nothing to do with quantum mechanics, but like the ground state of an oscillator, there is a quantum type of solution with a wavefunction of $\exp(-arr)$. In particular for the cylindrical coordinates:

$$-1/2m [1/r d/dr (r \exp(-a rr))] \exp(-arr) + V(r) \exp(-arr) = \text{constant} \exp(-a rr) \quad ((5))$$

where $V(r) = .5m\omega^2 r^2$ and $a = .5m\omega^2$ and $T = .5\omega^2$

$\exp(-a rr)$ in the quantum mechanical picture, however, may be considered to be a superposition of waves $\exp(i k \cdot r \text{vector})$. Sound waves have varying temperature (usually), but an interfering set of density waves without varying temperature could create the form $\exp(-a rr)$ in a quantum mechanical fashion in this classical problem. (3) The idea, we argue, is that $\exp(i k \cdot r \text{vector})$ type objects interfere to create an overall physical potential.

Classical Limit

The correspondence principle states that if one takes the high energy limit of a quantum solution, the classical spatial density should match the quantum envelope of spatial density.(4) In other words quantum mechanics still has peaks and troughs even in the classical limit, but these are separated by distances much smaller than dx in the classical region that they are not resolved. Thus only the envelope of the density $W^*(x)W(x)$ is considered even though it is not the full picture. The classical density (say for a bound state) is $C dt = C dx/|v|$ (4) where C is a

constant. For the bound state scenario, quantum mechanics includes both forward and backward motion (i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$) because it does not have a sharp time due to the nonlocality brought in by the wavelength. In the classical region, dt which would not be considered sharp in the quantum realm is considered to be sharp. Thus there is a fixed time point associated with dt in classical physics and one may link this to x . In other words, x and t are no longer independent or decoupled as in the quantum bound state case. A particle moving forward at x is separated in time from the scenario in which it moves backwards at the same x . In the classical realm, the quantum rms velocity becomes the “velocity” of interest and as $KE(x)$ quantum = $KE(x)$ classical, v_{rms} changes in the proper classical way. There is no density from $W^*(x)W(x)$ (troughs and peaks cannot be resolved) except for the envelope which is equal to $Cdx/|v|$ which is the classical result. Note the quantum strong measurement average of kinetic energy is: $W^* (-1/2m d/dx dW/dx) = (W^*W) KE(x)$ where $KE(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy. If W^*W does not display peaks/troughs then only the envelope is visible i.e. $Cdx/|v|$ which is also classical.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in both classical and quantum mechanics a particle tries to create a “potential (or force) profile” in space. In the classical scenario, p (momentum) at x is linked to an impulse (force) (e.g. the particle could strike an object with its momentum). The particle and object, however, must be able to interact through e.g. the electrostatic or strong nuclear force etc. In quantum mechanics there is the added feature that a quantum particle senses a direction along p and perpendicular to p and these are linked to the probability profile $\exp(ipx)$ (two dimensional). Thus there is nonlocality linked to an ambiguity in time (as there are various x values) and a probability profile which ultimately leads to a spatial density profile if superposition occurs as in a bound state or two slit experiment etc. In such a case, there is an average pressure linked to $[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx] / W$ multiplied by density $W^*(x)W(x)$. The density usually contains peaks and troughs and so creates a potential with a resolution pattern.

A classical analogue is given by a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in a cylinder rotating about its axis. This problem may be solved using a Schrodinger kind of equation written in cylindrical coordinates to yield a wavefunction of $\exp(-arr)$ which squared yields the density of classical statistical mechanics. (The ground state oscillator also has this property.) Thus one may consider classical waves $\exp(i p \cdot r_{vector})$ as superposing to create the wavefunction $\exp(-arr)$ which leads to the spatial density $\exp(-2a rr)$. In addition, a potential field is created as in the quantum case.

As noted, a quantum particle decouples space and time as: $d \text{Action}/dt = -E$ and $d\text{Action}/dx=p$ for a free particle Action (relativistic or nonrelativistic). This seems to be linked to the idea of time ambiguity due to spatial ambiguity associated with the wavelength. In the classical realm, the wavelength, which is proportional to $1/p$, becomes much smaller than dx at x , but x is considered to be a point. Likewise, time values associated within dx are essentially similar to a fixed t at x . In the quantum case, x points within the wavelength are associated with different times so one may even have $\exp(ipx)$ interfere with $\exp(-ipx)$. In classical mechanics it is as if each x is associated with a specific time and one may no longer resolve spatial density

humps with dx . As a result in the quantum high energy limit all that matters is $KE(x) * envelope(W*W)$ which matches the classical value $KE(x) Cdx/|v|$. As a result, time and space are no longer decoupled and one has locality albeit using regions dx where dx is said to shrink to zero and the times within dx to a single time of t . Thus $exp(ipx)$ and $exp(-ipx)$ interfere in the quantum realm due to time decoupling, but p and $-p$ at x are considered to occur at distinct times in classical mechanics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Quantum Wavelength as Related to an Impulse (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Yarman, T. and Kolmetskii, A. and Tane, J.L. The Ideal Gas Behaviour Is In Fact Nothing But A Macroscopic Quantum Mechanical Manifestation (2008 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0902.2636.pdf>
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. U. of Wisconsin-Madison 1995.
4. Majernik, Vladimir; Richterek, Lukas (1997-12-01). "[Entropic uncertainty relations for the infinite well](#)". J. Phys. A. 30 (4): L49. [Bibcode:1997JPhA...30L..49M](#). [doi:10.1088/0305-4470/30/4/002](#).